

PARAMETRIC AND STOCHASTIC FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF INTERPHASE EFFECTS IN COMPOSITE SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

As it is quite difficult, even impossible to characterize the interphase layer in a composite system because it is in general experimentally unaccessible, assumptions have to be made to model it. In a first instance a parametric finite element study for the interphase geometrical as well as mechanical properties is performed to quantify its influence on structural properties of a single lap joint. Stochastic aspects are investigated in a further analyse as an alternative approach to the classical design of composite systems in which variations are of paramount importance.

Keywords: micro-level model of interphase, stochastic treatment, Monte Carlo techniques.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite structural elements and systems are extensively used in advanced applications, due to their inherent qualities as high strength-to-weight, stiffness-to-weight ratios, and damage tolerance. Different materials are combined to form a new material, which exhibits the best qualities of its constituents, or even new properties neither of components possesses. Beside this properties improvement, there are other aspects, inherent to composite systems, that may affect the structural behaviour, as the interface/interphase phenomenon. In composite systems (e.g. fiber/matrix composite, adhesive joints,...) the interface effects are of high importance, although not yet completely understood.

The contact between the constituent materials does not arise through a straight interface, instead, the surface treatment applied to improve this contact between the bulk materials affects the properties of the material at the surface. A surface layer appears, which has a different composition and morphology from the bulk material. This layer has generally a non zero thickness, and will be referred as the *interphase*. Considering polymer matrix composite, the presence alone of the elastic fibre disturbs the viscoelastic properties of the matrix, and the surface treatment applied to the fiber (sizing) modifies even more the materials properties at the boundary region. Considering adhesive joints, the surface treatment applied to the adherends prior to bonding, creates a surface layer which exhibits totally different properties from those of the bulk material, as oxides layers on metallic adherends. The bonding process itself creates an intermediate layer between adherend and adhesive, with other properties than the bulk material properties. The bonding phenomenon arises from mechanical and chemical effects on this layer.

The problem is that the characteristics (mechanical properties, thickness, morphology,...) of those interphases can not be simply determined as they are generally not accessible for measurement, in their operating conditions. Physico-chemical tests, fragmentation test, pull-out test,... are all experimental methods which yield to an interphase characterization by one variable, or an

integrated expression of properties, and they are more suitable to compare different systems than to characterize completely a system. Where the interest is in the design and analysis of mechanical behaviour of composite systems, taking the interphase effects into account, those methods do not yield the necessary information about the interphase.

Continuum mechanics models have been proposed to characterize the interphase: an improved law of mixture for fibrous composites introducing the mesophase concept [1 - 2], continuum mechanics models [3-4] based on integrated moduli to relate the thermomechanical properties of the interphase to the experimental "single number" characterization.

The finite element method is proposed as an alternative approach to help characterizing interphases, and to quantify their influence on the macromechanical properties of composites systems. The aim of this study is to improve the understanding of the interphase nature, its effects on structural behaviour and damage, by a mechanical approach based on experiments and simulation by finite element modelling.

2. FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

2.1. Methodology

The finite element method is used at two level in the study of a single lap joint:

- The first model, at macroscopic level, with a low degree of refinement, is use to model the complete structure under investigation, using deterministic material properties, and no interphase effect. The macromechanical variables affecting the model behaviour are investigated.
- The second model, at microscopic scale, zooms on the critical region of the interphase, where the highest stresses occur. It is combined with a mesh refinement. Both models are coupled by geometrical considerations on the boundary conditions: the displacements imposed on the micro-level model are values interpolated from the previous using the shape functions of the element. Stochastic properties are assumed for the materials in this model, that is, the properties are supposed to follow a given statistical distribution, and not to have a defined value. Given the distribution functions for the material properties, that is, their type and values of parameters, a random number generation program using either an inversion or a transformation technique is used to generate deviates from those distributions. The random values of the stochastic properties are then assigned to the elements of the micro-level model by means of a Monte Carlo simulation. This analysis generates a stress pattern which is then averaged in the previous model.

2.2 Multilayered micro-level model

An adhesively bonded joint can be considered as a composite system: the processing of the adherend prior to bonding, and the development of the adhesion process yield to an interphase region between the bulk adhesive and the bulk adherend, leading to a multilayered system, as illustrated on Figure 1.

The single lap joint is modelled by a 2D structure, with quadratic elements, in plane strain conditions, and the micro-level model is built on the same assumptions. The boundary conditions applied to the latter are interpolated from the nodal displacements of the macro-level model, knowing the shape functions of the elements that are in this case quadratic. The zone of interest is the critical region of the joint, i.e. the end of the overlap. In the first instance, the interphase is introduced into the micro-level model as a layer of uniform thickness, whose value is approximated by experimental measurements on oxides layers of aluminium, as metallic adherends are considered in this paper. Typically, the thickness of such oxides layers is of the order of 0.5 μm to 5 μm , depending on the surface treatment [5-6].

Figure 1. Multilayered model for adhesively bonded system

As the mechanical properties of the interphase are not experimentally determined, assumptions have to be made concerning the evolution of those properties between the bulk adherend and adhesive. In the first instance, the mechanical properties attributed to the interphase are supposed to vary linearly on the thickness, interpolated between the properties of the two bonded materials. The number of elements in the thickness of the interphase determines the accuracy of this linear variation, i.e., if only one row of elements is used, the mean value of the properties of bulk adhesive and bulk adherend are attributed to those elements.

To have an idea of the influence of the interphase properties on the stress pattern, different variations are assumed for those properties, as illustrated on Figure 3.

Figure 3. Variation laws of properties on interphase thickness.

When considering the analysis performed to determine the dominant factors on structural behaviour of a single lap joint, and the high variability of the latter when one comes to practice, it could be advantageous to model those effects using stochastic tools. It has been shown that the preparation process prior to bonding is subjected to high variations, and that the effect of environmental factors as humidity and temperature are quite important on the adhesion process, and consequently on the interphase itself [7].

To take those uncertainties into account in the micro-level model, the stochastic aspects are introduced into the model with elastic material properties in the first instance. Concerning the

material stochastic variations, the properties are supposed to follow a given statistical distribution, and not to have a defined value [8]. Those distributions are experimentally determined, the materials considered here being the aluminium alloy 2024-T3 and modified epoxy adhesive FM73M, as indicated in Table 1. The stochastic distribution for the interphase properties are not experimentally available and are assumed to be uniform in the first instance. Further investigation has to be performed to check the validity of this assumption, and to evaluate the influence of the choice of the distribution. Given the distribution functions for the material properties, that is, their type and values of parameters, a random number generation program using either an inversion or a transformation technique is used to generate deviates from those distributions. The random values of the stochastic properties are then assigned to the elements of the micro-level model.

Table 1. Aluminium and Adhesive data.

Material:	Property:	strength	Young's modulus	Poisson's ratio
Aluminium:		Weibull (corr. = 0.983) $\eta = 481.6950$ $\sigma = 482.4364$	Weibull (corr. = 0.962) $\eta = 58.8986$ $\sigma = 72.7797$	Log- Normal (corr. = 0.893) $\mu = -1.1143$ $\sigma = 0.0097$
Adhesive:		Log- Normal (corr. = 0.966) $\mu = 3.8712$ $\sigma = 0.0120$	Log- Normal (corr. = 0.985) $\mu = 0.9187$ $\sigma = 0.0537$	Log- Normal (corr. = 0.893) $\mu = -0.9405$ $\sigma = 0.0319$

The Monte Carlo simulation consists now in assigning other random values to each element, determining the variable of interest, in this case the stress pattern and its maximum value, and repeating the procedure in order to obtain sufficient data to build up the statistical distribution of the state variable[8].

The first analyses on linear and parabolic evolution laws show some differences in the stress pattern and the maximum value, and the stochastic variation of the materials properties are of the same order (5% variation in properties changes induce a 10% variation on the stress). The results are quite sensitive to the number of elements in the interphase layer, as it determines the difference (jump) in material properties between the adjacent elements. Further investigation, with more refined mesh, has to be performed to analyse quantitatively the variation of properties through the thickness of the interphase, taking into account more abrupt variations.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENTS

Finite element modelling of a single lap joint allows the determination of the stress pattern in the whole structure, and of the most important factors on joint behaviour. Interphase effects are taken into account in a micro-level model, which is a zoom on the critical part of the joint, at the end of the overlap. Random material properties generated from experimentally validated statistical distributions are used as input for finite element model, one value being assigned to each element. Assumptions are made for the interphase properties evolution through the thickness, as well as for their statistical distribution. By repeating the process, this procedure allows the determination of the statistical distribution of the stress in the micro-level model. In this case, simulation is necessary to compensate the lack of information of available data.

This model yields some information on the influence of interphase characteristics on stress patterns. Influence on the macro-level model has to be further investigated.

The technique and results obtained in this first stage will be used for monitoring the progression of damage, based on the probability of failure calculated according to the stress field found in the

single lap joint. Interphase influence will be investigated more deeply, according to the assumptions that could be made on the nature and behaviour of the interphase, and related to joint strength.

4. REFERENCES

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